

Right To Compensation of Acid Attack Victims In India: Constitutional Foundations, Statutory Framework and Judicial Responses

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Abstract

Justice R. M. Lodha – Acid Attack as a Crime Against Human Dignity

“Acid attack is one of the most heinous crimes which not only disfigures the victim but also leaves a permanent scar on the victim’s dignity, self-respect and social life.”
(*Laxmi v Union of India*, (2014) 4 SCC 427)

Acid attacks represent one of the most brutal forms of violent crime, primarily targeting women and resulting in permanent physical disfigurement, severe psychological trauma, and long-term social and economic marginalisation of survivors. Beyond the immediate bodily harm, acid violence destroys dignity, identity, and the ability of victims to lead an autonomous and meaningful life, thereby constituting a grave violation of fundamental human rights.

In India, the legal response to acid attacks has gradually evolved from an offender-centric criminal justice model to a victim-centric framework that recognises compensation and rehabilitation as enforceable constitutional rights. Drawing strength from **Articles 14 and 21 of the Constitution of India**, the Supreme Court’s doctrine of **public law compensation**, **Section 357-A of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973**, and its successor **Section 396 of the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023**, victim compensation is no longer a matter of State charity or executive discretion. It constitutes a **binding constitutional obligation**, firmly rooted in the principles of **human dignity, equality, and restorative justice**, requiring the State to meaningfully rehabilitate victims of crime.[1]

Keywords

Acid Attack; Victim Compensation; Right to Life with Dignity; Article 21 of the Constitution; Gender-Based Violence; Victim-Centric Criminal Justice; Section 357-A CrPC and Section 396 BNSS; Victim Compensation Scheme; Central Victim Compensation Fund; Restorative Justice; Judicial Oversight.

Introduction

Acid attacks are among the most brutal forms of violence, leaving survivors with permanent disfigurement, disability and profound psychological trauma.

In India, the legal response has progressively moved from an offender-centric model to a victim-centric framework that recognises compensation and rehabilitation as enforceable rights. This framework is anchored in Articles 14 and 21 of the Constitution, strengthened by Section 357-A of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 (and its successor Section 396 of the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023), and concretised through the Supreme Court’s decisions in *Laxmi v. Union of India* and *Parivartan Kendra v. Union of India*. High Courts such as the Delhi and Kerala High Courts have further developed these principles by enforcing minimum compensation, condemning arbitrary reductions and reading a “bounden duty” to compensate into Section 357-A.

Acid attacks occupy a particularly disturbing place in the spectrum of violent crime. The impact of an acid attack is not limited to physical burns: survivors face repeated surgeries, loss of vision or other bodily functions, chronic pain, psychological trauma, and severe social stigma.[2]

Responding to growing public outrage, Parliament criminalised acid attacks specifically through Sections 326-A and 326-B of the Indian Penal Code, 1860 (IPC), inserted by the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2013.[3] These provisions, now substantially re-enacted in Section 124 of the Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023 (BNS), prescribe a minimum ten-year sentence and require that the fine imposed be “just and reasonable” to meet the medical expenses of the victim and be paid to the victim.[4]

Yet, punishment of the offender alone does not secure rehabilitation and dignified life for the survivor. The costs of long-term treatment, cosmetic and reconstructive surgery, psychological counselling and loss of livelihood often far exceed any fine that a trial court may impose. This has pushed Indian law towards a victim-centric understanding of criminal justice, where the State assumes a positive duty to provide compensation and support.

The right to compensation of acid attack victims in India today rests on a multi-layered

foundation: constitutional remedies under Articles 32 and 226; the statutory Victim Compensation Scheme (VCS) under Section 357-A CrPC / Section 396 BNSS; targeted policy instruments such as the CVCF and PMNRF; and a rich body of Supreme Court and High Court jurisprudence. This article traces that evolution and evaluates how far it has been effective in practice. This research paper examines the right to compensation of acid attack victims in India through four lenses: (i) the evolution of constitutional doctrine on State liability and victim compensation; (ii) the statutory and policy framework, including the Victim Compensation Scheme, Central Victim Compensation Fund (CVCF) and the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund (PMNRF); (iii) leading Supreme Court and High Court jurisprudence on acid attack compensation; and (iv) persistent implementation gaps. It concludes that a robust, timely and adequately funded compensation regime is normatively justified as a form of restorative constitutional justice and practically indispensable for the meaningful rehabilitation of acid attack survivors.

Objective of study

The aim of the study is to **critically analyse the right to compensation of acid attack victims in India**, with reference to its constitutional basis, statutory framework, and judicial development, and to assess whether the existing regime ensures effective, timely, and dignified rehabilitation.

1. To examine the constitutional foundations of victim compensation under Articles 14 and 21 of the Indian Constitution.
2. To analyse the evolution of public law compensation jurisprudence in India.
3. To study the statutory framework under Section 357-A CrPC and Section 396 BNSS.
4. To evaluate policy instruments such as the Victim Compensation Scheme, CVCF, PMNRF and NALSA schemes.
5. To examine Supreme Court and High Court jurisprudence on acid attack compensation.
6. To identify implementation gaps and systemic deficiencies.
7. To suggest legal and institutional reforms for strengthening victim-centric justice.

Review of Literature

Early constitutional jurisprudence in *Rudul Sah and Nilabati Behera* laid the foundation for public law compensation as a remedy for violation of fundamental rights.^[5] Scholars have recognised these decisions as transformative in establishing State liability for constitutional wrongs. Victimology literature emphasises that survivors of violent crimes such as acid attacks require long-term rehabilitation that cannot be addressed through criminal punishment alone.

Academic analyses of *Laxmi v. Union of India* highlight its significance in constitutionalising victim compensation and prescribing a national minimum standard, while also noting weaknesses in enforcement. Commentaries on *Parivartan Kendra* underline the Court's recognition that compensation must be adequate and individualised.^[6] Policy-oriented literature on the Victim Compensation Scheme and CVCF identifies delay, lack of awareness, and bureaucratic interpretation as persistent barriers. Recent High Court studies reveal growing judicial insistence on minimum compensation, yet continued disparity between law and practice. Overall, the literature supports the conclusion that while the normative framework is robust, its effectiveness depends on institutional coordination and sustained judicial oversight.

Methodology

The study adopts a **doctrinal and analytical research methodology**. Primary sources include constitutional provisions, statutory enactments (CrPC, BNSS, IPC, BNS), Supreme Court and High Court judgments, and official policy documents. Secondary sources include books on victimology, law commission reports, journal articles, government advisories, and NALSA publications. Recent judicial developments (2024–2025) have been analysed to reflect the contemporary legal position. A critical approach is employed to evaluate the gap between normative standards and practical implementation.

Analysis

CONSTITUTIONAL EVOLUTION OF VICTIM COMPENSATION

A. From State Liability to Public Law Compensation

The Supreme Court's jurisprudence on public law compensation for violation of fundamental rights is the doctrinal bedrock on which acid-attack compensation stands.

In *Rudul Sah v. State of Bihar*, the petitioner was kept in jail for over fourteen years after his acquittal. The Court held that where a person's liberty under Article 21 is unlawfully deprived, the Supreme Court can award monetary compensation under Article 32 as an appropriate remedy, instead of relegating the victim to a civil suit.

In *Nilabati Behera v. State of Orissa*, dealing with custodial death, the Court reaffirmed that compensation is available in public law for violation of fundamental rights, distinguishing it from private law remedies in tort and criminal proceedings.^[7] The judgment underlined that the State cannot escape liability for its agents' constitutional wrongs by invoking sovereign immunity.

In *Delhi Domestic Working Women's Forum v. Union of India*, a PIL concerning gang rape, the Court directed the establishment of a Criminal Injuries Compensation Board and stressed that rape survivors must be provided both legal aid and compensation.^[8] This marked an important shift from offender-focused criminal procedure to a model that also recognises the needs and rights of victims.

More recently, in *Nipun Saxena v. Union of India*, the Court, while dealing with sexual

offences, approved a Model Victim Compensation Scheme and clarified that compensation under Section 357-A CrPC is payable from a dedicated Victim Compensation Fund created by the State.[9].

These cases collectively recast compensation not as charity but as a constitutional remedial right arising from Article 21 and enforceable through Articles 32 and 226.

B. International Norms: UN Victims' Declaration

The Indian position is consistent with the **UN Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power (1985)**, which urges States to ensure that victims receive restitution and compensation for harm suffered, and that the State supplements or replaces offender-funded compensation where necessary[10]. This international framework supports the view that the State bears an affirmative obligation to repair serious criminal harms, such as acid attacks, especially when private compensation is inadequate or impossible.

II. STATUTORY FRAMEWORK: CRPC / BNSS AND IPC / BNS

A. Penal Provisions on Acid Attacks

Sections 326-A and 326-B IPC criminalise acid attacks and attempted acid attacks. Section 326-A prescribes a minimum punishment of ten years' imprisonment (extendable to life) and mandates a fine "which shall be just and reasonable to meet the medical expenses of the treatment of the victim" and "shall be paid to the victim." [11] Section 326-B deals with attempt and prescribes imprisonment of not less than five years.[12]

The **Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023** consolidates these offences in Section 124 BNS, substantially reproducing the ingredients and the requirement that fine be used to meet the victim's medical expenses.[13]. While this is an important recognition of the victim's financial needs, in practice the offender's ability to pay is often limited; hence the need for State-funded compensation.

B. Victim Compensation Scheme: Section 357-A CrPC and Section 396 BNSS

The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 was amended in 2008 to insert Section 357-A, which mandates that every State Government, in coordination with the Central Government, prepare a Victim Compensation Scheme for providing funds for compensation to victims or their dependents who have suffered loss or injury and require rehabilitation.[14].

1. Key features include:

1. Courts may recommend compensation to the District or State Legal Services Authority even where the case ends in acquittal or where the offender is not traced or identified.
2. The Legal Services Authority, after due inquiry, decides the quantum and disburses the amount.
3. Compensation under Section 357-A is in addition to any fine or compensation ordered under Section 357 CrPC.

The Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023 retains this scheme as Section 396 BNSS, further clarifying that victim compensation[15] is independent of, and supplemental to, the criminal sentence and fines. This statutory framework provides the principal legal gateway through which acid attack survivors may claim State compensation.

III. POLICY ARCHITECTURE: CVCF, PMNRF AND NALSA SCHEME

A. Central Victim Compensation Fund (CVCF) and Nirbhaya Fund

To strengthen the VCS, the Union Government created the Central Victim Compensation Fund (CVCF) using monies from the Nirbhaya Fund. Government guidelines fix certain minimum amounts for particular categories of victims, including acid attack survivors. For acid attacks, the CVCF prescribes a minimum of ₹3,00,000 per victim, with States free to prescribe higher amount[16]. The CVCF can be used both to support State schemes and to "top up" compensation where State amounts fall below the central minimum.

B. Additional Assistance from PMNRF

Recognizing that ₹3 lakh is often inadequate, the Ministry of Home Affairs issued an advisory providing additional assistance from the Prime Minister's National Relief Fund (PMNRF). Under this, acid attack victims are to receive an extra ₹1,00,000 in addition to amounts from the Victim Compensation Scheme.[17]. In practice, survivors in some States have received composite packages of ₹5 lakh (₹4 lakh from State/CVCF and ₹1 lakh from PMNRF), although frequently after long delays.[18].

C. NALSA (Legal Services to Victims of Acid Attacks) Scheme, 2016

In 2016, the National Legal Services Authority (NALSA) issued the Legal Services to Victims of Acid Attacks Scheme, recognizing acid attack survivors as a priority category for free legal aid. The scheme obliges Legal Services Authorities to:

1. Assist in registration of FIR and in the criminal trial;
2. Facilitate applications under the VCS and PMNRF;
3. Coordinate with health authorities to ensure free medical treatment; and
4. Aid access to disability benefits, educational and employment schemes.[19].

The legal architecture is therefore not merely punitive, but aspires to be restorative and rehabilitative.

IV. SUPREME COURT JURISPRUDENCE ON ACID ATTACK COMPENSATION

A. *Laxmi v. Union of India* case (2014) 4 SCC 427

The Supreme Court in *Laxmi v. Union of India* laid the constitutional foundation for a victim-centric framework addressing acid attacks in India. The Court recognised acid attacks as a grave violation of human dignity and held that the State bears a non-delegable constitutional obligation to prevent such crimes and rehabilitate victims.

Invoking Articles 14 and 21, the Court ruled that the right to life includes the right to live with dignity, which necessarily encompasses medical care, rehabilitation, and compensation for acid attack survivors. Compensation was declared a matter of constitutional duty, not executive discretion, extending the doctrine of public law compensation to victims of acid violence.

To operationalise this right, the Court mandated a minimum uniform compensation of ₹3,00,000 for every acid attack victim under Section 357-A CrPC, with immediate interim relief and subsequent rehabilitative support. It further directed free medical treatment in both government and designated private hospitals, ensuring that lack of financial means does not impede access to care.

The judgment also addressed prevention by imposing strict regulation on the sale of acid, including identity verification, record-keeping, reporting obligations, and prohibition of sale to minors. Institutional accountability was reinforced by assigning monitoring responsibilities to State and District Legal Services Authorities.

Overall, the *Laxmi* judgment transformed acid attack compensation from a welfare measure into an enforceable fundamental right, established national uniformity in victim compensation, and paved the way for subsequent judicial and policy developments strengthening restorative justice and gender-sensitive victim rights jurisprudence in India.

Impact and Follow-Up

The *Laxmi* case led to sweeping reforms:

- States revised their Victim Compensation Schemes, fixing the 3 lakh minimum.
- The Central Victim Compensation Fund (CVCF) was later established in 2015, using the Nirbhaya Fund, to support these payments.
- Subsequent judgments such as *Parivartan Kendra v. Union of India* (2016) 3 SCC 571 expanded on *Laxmi* by suggesting ₹10 lakh as an appropriate compensation in severe cases.
- Legal recognition was given to acid attack survivors as persons with disabilities, entitling them to job reservations and welfare schemes.

Significance

The *Laxmi* judgment:

1. Constitutionalised victim compensation by making it a part of the right to life.
2. Established a national minimum standard for compensation and free medical care.
3. Introduced institutional accountability via Legal Services Authorities.

B. *Parivartan Kendra v. Union of India*: From Minimum to Adequate Compensation

In *Parivartan Kendra v. Union of India*, the petitioner NGO highlighted the plight of acid attack survivors who, despite *Laxmi*, had not received adequate compensation or rehabilitation.^[20] The Supreme Court:

1. Reiterated that ₹3 lakh is a mandatory minimum under State VCS for acid attack victims and criticized States for non-compliance.^[21]
2. Observed that ₹3 lakh is often insufficient to cover the cost of surgeries and long-term care, and awarded ₹10 lakh to one of the petitioners, indicating that higher amounts should be considered based on the severity and consequences of the attack.^[22]
3. Directed that acid attack victims be treated as persons with disability, eligible for benefits under disability law, including reservation in jobs and education.^[23]
4. Emphasized holistic rehabilitation: medical treatment, psychological counselling and gainful employment.

Parivartan Kendra deepens the *Laxmi* framework by making clear that the ₹3 lakh requirement is a floor, not a ceiling, and that compensation must be individualized to the survivor's needs

C. Recent Supreme Court Oversight (2024–2025)

In recent years, the Supreme Court has continued to monitor implementation of its directions on compensation and treatment of acid attack survivors. In March 2025,^[24] while hearing a continuing PIL on efficient compensation for victims of acid attacks, the Court recorded information from NALSA that around ₹484 crore had been disbursed as victim compensation between March 2024 and April 2025, but expressed concern about persisting delays and non-payment in individual cases. It granted liberty to all acid attack survivors to approach their State Legal Services Authorities (SLSAs) directly if compensation was delayed or defaulted, and directed SLSAs to submit charts showing applications received and amounts disbursed. The Court also reiterated that survivors are

legally entitled to at least ₹3,00,000, with ₹1,00,000 within 15 days and the remaining ₹2,00,000 within two months, and that private hospitals must provide free emergency treatment in line with earlier orders.

In the same set of proceedings, the Bench sharply criticised “severe gaps in critical care” for survivors and non-compliance by many private hospitals in providing cashless treatment, calling upon the Union and States to frame effective protocols for immediate admission, surgery and follow-up care. This confirms that the Court treats the compensation and medical-care framework as a continuing constitutional obligation, subject to ongoing judicial supervision. Separately, in December 2025, another Bench of the Supreme Court, dealing with an acid-attack case where the victim was allegedly forced to ingest acid, held that such attackers should ordinarily be charged with attempt to murder (Section 307 IPC/BNS) rather than only as grievous-hurt offences, describing acid attackers as a “threat to society” and noting the permanent impact on victims’ bodies and dignity. [25]

IV. HIGH COURT DEVELOPMENTS: ENFORCING THE RIGHT ON THE GROUND

A. Delhi High Court: No Reduction Below Minimum Compensation

The Delhi High Court has played a leading role in operationalising the Laxmi Parivartan Kendra framework through the Delhi Victim Compensation Scheme, 2015/2018. The Scheme prescribes ₹3,00,000 as minimum compensation for acid attack victims, with ₹1,00,000 payable within fifteen days as interim relief. [26]

In **Rachna Paul v. Government of NCT of Delhi**, the Criminal Injuries Compensation Board had awarded only ₹30,000 as interim compensation to an acid attack survivor who suffered around 5–6% burns, treating it as a minor injury case. [27] The High Court held:

1. Acid attack victims constitute a distinct category under the Scheme and cannot be equated with other hurt cases on the basis of injury percentage alone.
2. Once the competent authority decides to grant compensation under the Scheme, it cannot reduce the amount below the minimum of ₹3,00,000 prescribed for acid attack victims, even where the assessed burns are less than 50 per cent. [28]
3. The Scheme must be interpreted consistently with Laxmi and Parivartan Kendra, which read the minimum compensation requirement into Article 21.

This judgment converts the Supreme Court’s normative directions into a hard legal floor at the State level, invalidating arbitrary under-compensation

In April 2024, the Delhi High Court directed the Delhi State Legal Services Authority (DSLISA) to pay ₹5,00,000 each to two acid attack victims, observing that heinous crimes like rape and acid attack warrant robust victim-centric measures. The Court further asked DSLISA and the Delhi Government to explore employment opportunities within government departments for the survivors, linking compensation to long-term rehabilitation and economic independence. [29]

In December 2024, in **Preeti v. State & Anr.**, a Division Bench of the Delhi High Court approved and directed implementation of the “Avlamban Fund Scheme, 2024” for acid attack survivors in the National Capital Territory. The Scheme creates a permanent corpus of ₹10 crore to provide sustained financial support, including lump-sum grants and periodic assistance, for survivors who are residents of Delhi or whose attacks occurred in Delhi, irrespective of their current address. The Court directed that the Scheme be administered by the Principal District & Sessions Judge and applied in a broad, inclusive manner so that survivors are not excluded on technical grounds. [30]

B. Recent High Courts Decisions on Compensation (2022–2025)

Apart from Delhi, several other High Courts and trial courts have contributed to the evolving jurisprudence on acid attack compensation.

(1) Amanpreet Kaur v. Union of India (Punjab & Haryana High Court, 2022)

In **Amanpreet Kaur v. Union of India**, the petitioner, an acid attack survivor with 50% permanent disability and loss of vision in one eye, approached the High Court seeking proper implementation of compensation and medical-treatment policy. The Court recorded that compensation under the State policy and the Central Victim Compensation Fund (CVCF) had already been paid, but accepted that the survivor could not afford to pre-pay treatment costs and then seek reimbursement. It therefore directed the Punjab State Legal Services Authority to coordinate cashless treatment, paying the hospital directly under the existing policy. The judgment operationalizes the idea that victim compensation includes ensuring practical access to medical care, not merely sanctioning amounts on paper. [31]

In **April 2024**, the **Bombay High Court** [32] held that acid attack survivors cannot be denied compensation under the *Maharashtra Victim Compensation Scheme, 2022* on limitation grounds, as **Clause 16 permits condonation of delay in deserving cases**. The Court allowed survivors of a 2010 acid attack to apply under the Scheme and clarified that they are entitled to **full compensation without any cap**, in line with Supreme Court directions.

(2) Kerala High Court: Life Sentence and Binding Duty to Compensate

In *X v. State of Kerala (2025)*, the Kerala High Court upheld the conviction and life sentence of a man who poured acid on his partner and four children, and ordered the State to pay ₹3,00,000 to each of the five victims under Section 357-A CrPC. The Division Bench held that in acid attack cases it is the “bounden duty” of courts to ensure adequate compensation, and interpreted the word “may” in Section 357-A(3) as imposing a mandatory obligation on courts to consider compensation.^[33]

The judgment is notable because the High Court treated victim compensation as an integral part of the criminal justice outcome rather than as a collateral administrative matter, thereby reinforcing the notion of compensation as a judicially enforceable right.

V. THE CONTENT OF THE “RIGHT TO COMPENSATION” OF ACID ATTACK VICTIMS

Drawing together constitutional, statutory and judicial strands, the right to compensation of acid attack victims in India today includes the following elements:

The right to compensation of acid attack victims in India is grounded in **Articles 21 and 14** of the Constitution, as acid attacks violate the right to life with dignity and demand a non-arbitrary, victim-centric State response. Statutorily, **Section 357-A CrPC / Section 396 BNSS** enables victims to claim compensation from Legal Services Authorities irrespective of conviction or identification of the offender. The **Supreme Court of India** has mandated a minimum compensation of ₹3,00,000 per victim, supplemented by additional monetary reliefs and fines. The right further includes free medical treatment, legal aid, disability recognition, and is **continuing in nature**, not defeated by limitation.

VI. PROCEDURAL PATHWAYS FOR CLAIMING COMPENSATION

From a practical standpoint, the right to compensation must be coupled with clear procedural pathways.

1. Criminal Complaint and Investigation

- Registration of FIR under Section 326-A IPC / Section 124 BNS at the police station.
- Police should ensure immediate medical treatment and inform the concerned DLSA, in line with NALSA guidelines,

2. Application under Victim Compensation Scheme

- The survivor (or legal representative) files an application before the DLSA/SLSA, enclosing the FIR, medical reports, disability certificate, and details of expenses and loss of income.
- DLSA/SLSA conducts an inquiry and grants interim compensation for urgent medical needs, followed by final compensation based on severity, disability, and rehabilitation requirements,

3. PMNRF Assistance and Other Schemes

- District authorities can forward proposals for PMNRF assistance in eligible cases, yielding an additional ₹1 lakh for acid attack survivors.

4. Judicial Remedies

- If compensation is denied, unduly delayed or arbitrarily reduced below the normative minimum, the survivor may invoke the writ jurisdiction of the High Court under Article 226, relying on *Laxmi*, *Parivartan Kendra* and relevant State-scheme provisions.

VII. CRITICAL PERSPECTIVES: GAP BETWEEN LAW AND REALITY

Despite a sophisticated legal framework, the implementation record is far from satisfactory.

- **Delay:** Many survivors receive compensation years or decades after the attack, thereby undermining the purpose of “immediate relief.”
- **Inadequate Quantum:** Even ₹3–5 lakh is often nowhere near sufficient to cover multiple surgeries, reconstructive procedures, therapy and lifelong income loss; *Parivartan Kendra* explicitly acknowledged this inadequacy.
- **Lack of Awareness:** Survivors frequently learn about VCS, CVCF or PMNRF only through NGOs or chance interactions with officials.
- **Fragmented Services:** Medical, legal, psycho-social and livelihood support remain poorly coordinated, notwithstanding NALSA’s holistic vision.

These challenges suggest that the normative right to compensation is necessary but not sufficient; institutional reforms and proactive State practice are essential.

Conclusion

Indian criminal jurisprudence has gradually shifted from an offender-centric model to one that acknowledges the rights and dignity of victims, particularly in cases of acid attacks. Through constitutional interpretation and statutory intervention, compensation has emerged as a substantive right rather than a matter of discretion. Judicial recognition of public law compensation, combined with legislative measures under the criminal procedure framework, reflects an evolving commitment to restorative justice.

Yet, the effectiveness of this framework remains uneven due to delays, inconsistent standards, and weak administrative coordination. To strengthen the system, minimum compensation amounts must be clearly fixed in law and revised periodically to reflect economic realities. Compensation should be released within strict timelines, and the criminal justice machinery should initiate the process automatically once an acid attack offence is registered. Uniform national criteria for assessing compensation, coupled with meaningful rehabilitation through disability recognition, education, and employment support, are essential for long-term survivor reintegration. Finally, transparency through regular publication of data on compensation and rehabilitation outcomes is necessary to ensure accountability and informed policy reform.

Only by addressing these structural and procedural shortcomings can compensation for acid attack victims function as an effective instrument of dignity, recovery, and justice.

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